

THE EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF THE COMPRESSIVE PERFORMANCE OF PULTRUDED ROD COMPOSITE STRUTS

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Keywords: Pultruded composite struts, Eccentric buckling test, Compressive performance

ABSTRACT

Pultruded carbon fibre/epoxy composites possess high fibre alignment. However, the characterisation of the compression performance of these materials in axial compression loading is sensitive to the factors such as specimen end preparation, loading misalignment and localised non-uniform loading. End fittings have been used to prevent the premature failure of these materials in axial compression test but this induced high complexity of the preparation process. In this study, we developed aneccentric buckling test methodology to investigate the compressive performance of pultruded carbon fibre/epoxy composites. The test results showed that the elastic modulus (85.5 ± 1.3 GPa) and flexural modulus (87.3 ± 3.0 GPa) were consistent with the value measured from tensile test at 88 GPa. A compressive failure strain at failure at -0.0134 ± 0.0007 was measured, which is higher compared with the reported values in literature for carbon fibre/epoxy pultruded rods. This shows that the eccentric buckling test is suitable for measuring the compressive failure strain of carbon fibre/epoxy pultruded rods.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre/epoxy composites have been widely used in engineering applications due to their excellent mechanical performance. However, the material exhibits relatively weak compressive performance, partially due to fibre misalignment and waviness [1]. Pultruded carbon fibre/epoxy composites have been developed [2], with the applied pulling force in the pultrusion process to improve the fibre alignment of the resulting composites. Greater compressive performance is therefore expected.

Works have been conducted to characterise the compressive performance of the pultruded composites using the direct compression test method [3-6]. For example, carbon fibre/epoxy pultruded rods of 1.7 mm in diameter were bonded with metallic cylindrical holders and then loaded against upper and lower metal platens in compression until failure [3]. The results showed that stress concentration at the junction of gauge length and cylindrical holders was observed, and that the presence of voids and fibre misalignment resulted in reduced compressive strength. In another study, 6 mm diameter carbon fibre-polyester pultruded rods were snugly fitted into metallic end pieces and then tested in direct compression [4]. Test results showed that failure occurred at low compressive strain and reduced strength was measured, possibly due to stress concentration near specimen gauge section and specimen misalignment during mounting. Collars have been used to laterally support specimens upon compression. In summary, the direct compression test for pultruded rod composites requires extensive experience and skills on specimen preparation, endcap design and specimen mounting, to prevent incorrect load induction, stress concentration, buckling instability, and specimen end crushing and booming due to gripping and specimen misalignment [2].

Alternatively, some of the authors of the current work have developed a 'cradle' test method using 4-point bending [7]. Easycomposite Carbon fibre/epoxy pultruded rods of 0.8 mm in diameter have been

tested and a compressive failure strain of -0.0116 has been reported. However, the test method may not be suitable for large diameter pultruded rods due to the complex design of the cradle.

We have developed an eccentric buckling test methodology to investigate the compressive performance of 6 mm diameter pultruded carbon fibre/epoxy composites. Compressive failure strain was measured and compared with published data measured from other test methods. This method provides an alternative way to measure the compression behaviour of circular pultruded composite rods.

2 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

2.1 Materials

In this study, Easycomposite pultruded carbon fibre/epoxy (ECPRs) of 6 mm in diameter, purchased from Easycomposite, UK, were used in the development of this test method. The manufacturer's datasheet indicates an elastic modulus of 28-40 GPa [8] for the rod material but a much higher value of 132 GPa has been reported for 0.8 mm diameter ECPRs [7]. Tensile tests were therefore conducted to measure the elastic modulus of the ECPR strut specimens in this study.

2.2 Specimen preparation

The as-received ECPR struts of 6 mm in diameter and 1 meter long were cut into 300 mm long (i.e. an aspect ratio of 50:1 was used). Sections of the material were cast in epoxy resin and the polished cross section was examined under microscope.

Figure 1a shows the specimen dimensions. The ECPR struts were then marked with three longitudinal lines separated by 120° on the circumferential surface at the mid-span location. Three uniaxial strain gauges were subsequently bonded longitudinally at the marked lines. A line corresponding to one of the strain gauge positions was also marked close to each end of the strut to help align the end caps.

The ECPR struts with the strain gauges were CT-scanned (Zeiss Xradia 5200, DE) to determine the actual enclosed angles between strain gauges and to measure the diameter of the struts. After this, the ECPR struts were bonded with endcaps using an epoxy resin adhesive (3M DP490, UK). The endcap, shown in Figure 1b, is designed so that the strut axis is offset by 7 mm from the loading pin centre to promote bending. During bonding, the marked lines at each end of the ECPR strut was aligned with the engraved mark on the endcaps. This ensured that one strain gauge was aligned with the nominal position of the maximum compression stress in the strut upon testing. The curing of the adhesive followed the resin manufacturer's recommendation.

Figure 1: (a) ECPR strut dimension (mm) and (b) endcap design (mm).

The centre zone of 40 mm length of each ECPR strut was painted in white using an acrylic spray paint. Once fully dried, black speckles were applied onto the paint for strain measurement with digital image correlation (DIC).

2.3 Eccentric buckling tests

Eccentric buckling tests were conducted on an Instron 1341 test machine fitted with a 5 kN axial loadcell. Figure 2 shows the test setup. The specimen was mounted onto the test machine using pins inserted through the clearance holes in the endcaps and the fixture. The mounting ensured that the strut was pin-ended and would buckle in the yz plane. Spacers were used to ensure there was no eccentricity of loading in the x -direction. The specimen was loaded in displacement-control at a constant crosshead speed of 3 mm/min until failure.

Figure 2: The eccentric buckling test setup.

Stereo DIC with two 16 mega-pixel cameras (LaVision, DE) and external LED light arrays were used to capture the full-field strain development to capture the strain development in the central zone of the strut viewed in the y -direction. The pixel size was 0.0055 mm. The captured images were processed using Davis (LaVision, DE) with a subset size of 31 pixels and a step size of 15 pixels. The bonded strain gauges were connected to the strain gauge logger for strain measurement.

Load (F) was measured from the test machine and strains were recorded by both the bonded strain gauges and the DIC, at a constant sampling rate of 1 Hz.

2.4 Data reduction

The applied stress (σ) was calculated using the equation (1)

$$\sigma = \frac{F}{A} \quad (1)$$

where A is the cross-sectional area of the strut at the mid-span position.

The critical buckling stress (σ_b) is given by

$$\sigma_b = \frac{\pi^2 EI}{L^2} \quad (2)$$

where E is elastic modulus, I is the second moment of area and L is the length between the loading pin hole centres of the endcaps.

The strain in the strut at the mid-length position can be considered as the superposition of the axial strain (longitudinal strain acting at the centroid) and the bending strain which varies linearly over the cross-section. The axial and bending strains can be determined from the three strain gauge measurements.

Figure 3: The schematic diagram of the calculation of axial strain and compressive strain from the three strain gauge measurements.

At the mid-span cross section of an ECPR strut specimen, three direct strains (ϵ_1 , ϵ_2 , and ϵ_3) are measured at the strain gauge locations as shown in Figure 3. Assuming linear elasticity and that buckling and bending occur about the x -axis, the neutral axis (zero bending strain) lies along the x -axis. The

maximum tensile and compressive strains, occur at the top and bottom surfaces intersecting the y-axis. The axial strain can be derived from a set of three sine wave equations related with the direct strain recorded at the three strain gauges locations. For bending about the x-axis the following equations can be established

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon_1 &= A \sin \alpha + C \\ \varepsilon_2 &= A \sin(\alpha + \gamma) + C \\ \varepsilon_3 &= A \sin(\alpha + \beta) + C\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

where A is the magnitude of the bending strain at $y = \pm R$ (the radius of the circular cross-section), α is the unknown enclosed angle of the first strain gauge and the x-axis, β and γ are the enclosed angles between the first strain gauge and the second and third strain gauges respectively measured from CT-scan, and C is the axial strain.

From the equation set (3), and the CT-measured values of β and γ , the axial strain and the location and value of the maximum bending strain component can be determined.

The bending stress (σ_{bend}), assuming a linear elastic response, is given by the equation (4)

$$\sigma_{bend} = \frac{32F(\delta + e)}{\pi D^3} \quad (4)$$

where δ is the deflection measured from DIC, e is the initial eccentricity of the load, and D is the strut diameter.

Axial modulus (E) can be determined from the applied axial stress – axial strain plot and the flexural modulus (E_f) can be derived from the bending stress – bending strain plot. These were used to compare with the elastic modulus measured from the tensile tests to validate the proposed test methodology.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mechanical performance of pultruded struts

Figure 4 shows the applied axial stress – axial strain responses of a typical ECPR strut specimen subjected to eccentric buckling. The dotted line is the critical buckling stress and the axial strain is calculated from the set of the three sine wave equations assuming a linear response. It can be seen that the specimen failed before reaching the critical buckling stress, as expected. The axial modulus, taken from the slope of the initial linear region at axial strains from 0 to -0.0001, is 86 GPa. This is consistent with the elastic modulus of 88 GPa measured in the tensile test but is significantly lower than the published value of 132 GPa for 0.8 mm diameter ECPR measured from the cradle test [7].

The inserted DIC images in Figure 4 shows that the specimen exhibited variation from compressive strain to tensile strain over the strut diameter. However, unexpected bands of compressive strain and tensile strain across the strut diameter have been developed. These may be due to the poor speckle quality and need further investigation. The maximum compressive strain measured from strain gauge was -0.0135. However, initial failure was observed to be by fibre breakage on the tensile side of the strut. Further investigation into the occurrence of such tensile failure via an interrupted test will be conducted.

Figure 4: The applied stress – axial strain curve of a typical ECPR strut specimen subjected to eccentric buckling, with the inserted DIC images to show the compression-tension transition.

Figure 5 shows the bending stress – bending strain response of the same ECPR strut specimen at the compression side. The figure shows that a linear response of the material is observed, with the flexural modulus measured as 84 GPa. This is consistent with the axial modulus determined from the applied axial stress – axial strain plot.

Figure 5: The bending stress-strain plot of the typical ECPR strut specimen.

Table 1 summarises, for a set of 5 repeated tests, the average axial and flexural moduli, the average measured compressive failure strain from the strain gauge close to the peak compression position and

the average compressive failure strain calculated as the maximum determined from the three strain readings and locations of all three strain gauges. (Standard deviation values are given in brackets.) It shows that the axial modulus is consistent with the value measured separately from a tensile test at 88 GPa, and that the flexural modulus shows very good agreement with the axial modulus, as expected. The compressive failure strain, is significantly higher than the failure strain values reported in literatures, although these are for other pultruded carbon fibre/epoxy materials. For example, *Soutis* reported the compressive strain at -0.0092 of 4 mm diameter T300/828 pultruded rods [9] and *Vankar et al* measured the compressive strain of 6.5 mm diameter pultruded rods at -0.0036 [10]. The high compressive failure strain may be partially due to the strain gradient in a bending test [11]. The average compressive failure strain calculated from the set of the three sine wave equations is slightly higher than the average measured compressive failure strain determined from the strain gauge located on the compressive side of the strut, but this is as expected if the strain gauge is not perfectly positioned with the maximum compressive strain location.

Average elastic modulus [GPa]	Average flexural modulus [GPa]	Average measured compressive strain [S]	Average calculated compressive strain [S]
85.5 (1.3)	87.3 (3.0)	-0.0134 (0.0007)	-0.0145 (0.0010)

Table 1: The average mechanical properties of ECPR strut specimens subjected to eccentric buckling test.

3.2 Microscope examination

Figure 6 shows the microscope image of the cross-section of an ECPR strut specimen. It can be seen that fibre clusters, resin-rich region and voids were formed during the pultrusion process.

Figure 6: The microscope images of a ECPR specimen to indicate the fibre-rich region, neat resin region and voids. (20× magnification).

4 CONCLUSIONS

We have proposed an eccentric buckling test methodology to investigate the compressive

performance of large diameter pultruded carbon fibre/epoxy composites. ECPR struts of 6 mm in diameter were tested. The test results have shown that the axial modulus (85.5 ± 1.3 GPa) and flexural modulus (87.3 ± 3.0 GPa) were in good agreement with the value of 88 GPa measured in a tensile test. A compressive failure strain at failure of -0.0134 ± 0.0007 was measured, which is higher than values reported in the literature for other carbon fibre pultruded rods.

The next step of this study is to investigate the compressive performance of hierarchical pultruded rod epoxy composite struts developed within the NextCOMP research project.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors kindly acknowledge the funding for this research provided by UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) programme Grant EP/T011653/1, Next Generation Fibre-Reinforced Composites (NextCOMP): a Full Scale Redesign for Compression a collaboration between Imperial College London and the University of Bristol. Supporting data can be requested from the corresponding author but may be subject to confidentiality obligations.

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